

EFFECT OF WEAVE STRUCTURE ON MODE I INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE BEHAVIOUR OF PLAIN GLASS WOVEN FABRIC COMPOSITES AS A FUNCTION OF THE INTERFACE: REPORT OF A ROUND ROBIN TEST II

H.Saidpour & M.Sezen, *Bournemouth University, UK*

Y.J.Dong, H.S.Yang, Y.L.Bai & T.X.Mao, *Chinese Academy of Science, China*

C.Bathias, *CNAM/ITMA, France*

P.Krawczak, R.Bequignat & J.Pabiot, *Ecole des mines de Douai, France*

S.Pinter & G.Banhegyi, *Furukawa Electric Institute of Technology, Hungary*

J.K.Kim & M.L.Sham, *Hong Kong University of Science & Technology, Hong Kong*

I.Verpoest, *Katholike University of Leuven, Belgium*

H.Hamada, Y.Hirai & K.Fujihara, *Kyoto Institute of Technology, Japan*

C.Y.Yue & K.Padmanabhan, *Nanyang Technological University, Singapore*

Y.Suzuki, *Nitto Boseki Co.Ltd, Japan*

T.Tanimoto, *Shonan Institute of Technology, Japan*

K.Schlute, *Technical University Hamburg - Harburg, Germany*

J.K.Karger-Kocsis, *University of Kaiserslautern, Germany*

W.J.Cantwell & R.Zulkifli, *University of Liverpool, UK*

L.Ye, *University of Sydney, Australia*

A.Lowe, *Australia National University, Australia*

S.V.Hoa, *Concordia University, Canada*

V.V. Smirnov, *Metal - Polymer Resarch Institute BAS, Belarus*

L.T.Drzal, *Michigan State University, USA*

W.R Broughtor, *National Physical Laboratory, UK*

J.J.Lesko, *Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, USA*

SUMMARY: Short beam shear tests and mode I interlaminar fracture toughness tests are performed in a Round Robin Test (RRT) programme proposed by the Society of Interfacial Materials Science (SIMS) to characterize the interlaminar fracture behavior of E-glass woven fabric reinforced vinylester composites. Twenty institutions worldwide have participated in this programme. No specific guidelines are given for the details of the test and the data reduction schemes, so that the participating laboratories perform the tests in their own ways. Only the fiber orientations relative to the specimen length are specified i.e. warp and weft fiber specimens. The first report of this programme to be presented at the 11th International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM-11) focuses mainly on the effect of silane coupling agent on mode I interlaminar fracture toughness tests and the stability of crack propagation. In this report, the focus is placed on the influence of weave structure of reinforcement on interlaminar fracture behavior.

KEYWORDS: e-glass woven fabric reinforced vinylester composites; silane coupling agents; interface; interlaminar shear strength; mode I interlaminar fracture toughness; weave structure.

INTRODUCTION

The interphase of composite materials is a key part which plays an important role in determining the mechanical, chemical and degradation properties in composite materials. Hence, evaluations of the interphase properties in composite materials have been performed actively [1~4]. For instance, several testing methods (e.g. fiber fragmentation tests [3], embedded single fiber tests [4] etc.) have been developed to measure the bond quality at the interphase between the fiber and matrix resin. There are also other testing methods to evaluate the interphase using the bulk composite laminates based on short beam shear tests [5,6] and interlaminar fracture toughness tests [7,8].

E-glass woven fabric reinforced composites have been widely used in commercial application, such as printed circuit boards, water tanks and fishing boats. It is well known that surface treatment is generally performed on the glass surface with silane coupling agents to improve the bonding with the matrix resin. The structure of interphase in glass fiber reinforced composites is very complex chemically and physically, and there are many factors which affect the mechanical properties of the composites made therefrom. On performing surface treatment of glass fibers, optimum conditions in order to get good adhesion between the fiber and matrix resin were reported [9].

The Society of Interfacial Materials Science (SIMS) was established in 1993 to promote the understanding of composite interphases of various kinds as an interdisciplinary problem from the perspectives of chemistry, physics, material science and engineering mechanics. As part of its activities, the SIMS has organized the RRT programme to study the mechanical properties of E-glass woven fabric reinforced composites. The aim of the programme is to exchange the experiences between the participants and enhance the fundamental understanding of the composite interphase. In the first RRT (RRT-I) programme, the tensile and bending tests were performed by ten institutions. It was found that both tensile and bending strengths increased with increasing the concentration of methacryl silane. In the present second RRT (RRT-II) programme short beam shear tests and mode I interlaminar fracture toughness tests have been performed by twenty institutions. The first part of the report presents the results on the effect of surface treatment on mode I interlaminar fracture toughness. In this paper which is the second part of the report on the present RRT programme, a focus is placed on the effect of weave structure on interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) and mode I interlaminar fracture toughness. It is aimed to contribute to further understanding of interphase properties which are vital to mechanical properties of composite materials.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Material

Glass woven fabrics of 44 (warp) x 34 (weft) strands count per 2.5 cm x 2.5 cm were used as reinforcement (Nitto Boseki Co. Ltd., Japan). Fig.1 schematically illustrates the elements of

weave structure in glass woven fabric which are used in this study. The distance between the center of fiber strands was longer in the warp direction than in the weft direction, due to the difference in density of fiber strands. Surface treatment was performed on the glass fiber fabric by using γ -methacryloxypropyltrimethoxysilane (A-174, Nippon Unicar, Co., Japan) and γ -glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane (A-187, Nippon Unicar, Co., Japan), which are called methacryl silane and epoxy silane, respectively. The concentrations of silane agents were 0.01, 0.4, 1.0 wt% methacryl silane, 0.4 wt% methacryl silane washed with methanol solvent and 0.4 wt% epoxy silane. The aqueous solution of silane coupling agent was acidified with acetic acid at $\text{pH} = 4.0$. The glass fiber fabrics were dipped into the silane aqueous solutions. They were squeezed by rollers and dried at 110 degree C for 10 min. Vinylester resin (R-806, Syowa High Polymer, Japan) was polymerized with 0.7 phr methyl-ethyl-ketone-peroxide. Composite laminates were fabricated by hand lay-up technique. A 40 μm thick polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) was inserted as an initial crack during the lay-up at the mid-plane of the laminates for mode I interlaminar fracture toughness tests.

Fig.1 Schematic diagram of weave structure of glass woven fabrics: (a) warp specimens, (b) weft specimens.

Specimen Geometry and Test Condition

The SIMS fabricated and supplied the composite laminates whose thicknesses were specified by the individual participating laboratories. The participating laboratories decided the test speed, specimen geometry and so on. Typical specimen geometry for measuring interlaminar shear strength by short beam shear test was given in Fig.2 (a). The specimen was cut parallel and perpendicular to the warp strand direction, designating warp and weft specimens, respectively. Table 1 gives the details of the specimen dimensions and test conditions used by each laboratory. Short beam shear tests were performed on the specimens with all five surface treatments. The interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) was calculated according to specification BS2782 and ASTM D 2344:

$$\tau = 3P_{max} / 4wh \quad (1)$$

where P_{max} is the applied maximum load, w and h are the specimen width and thickness, respectively.

Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness tests were performed using double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens. Specimens finished 0.01 and 0.4 wt% methacryl silane were used. Typical geometry and details dimension of DCB specimen are shown in Fig.2 (b) and Table 2. Either aluminium blocks or piano hinges were bonded to the specimen edges to allow loading in tension. Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness, G_{IC} and G_{IR} , were calculated

according to data reduction scheme chosen by the individual laboratories. The details are reported in the first part of this report [10].

Table 1 Specimen dimensions and data reduction schemes on interlaminar shear strength test.

List number	Affiliations	Width W	Thickness h	Length L	Span length D	Cross-head speed (mm/min)	Data reduction scheme*
1.	B.U.	10	3	18	15	1.0	BS2782
4.	E.M.D.	10	3	18	15	1.0	ASTM D 2344
6.	H.K.U.S.T.	6.4	4	28	20	1.3	ASTM D 2344
9.	N.T.U.	10	2.95 ± 0.05	24	16	1.2	ASTM D 2344
12.	U.K.	10	4	28	19	1.0	ASTM D 2344

Table 2 Specimen dimensions and data reduction schemes on mode I interlaminar fracture toughness test.

List number	Affiliations	Width W*	Thickness 2h*	Length L*	Crack length a	Cross-head speed (mm/min)	Data reduction scheme*
4.	E.M.D.	20	3	125-180	25-80	1.0	A
5.	F.E.I.T.	10	3	270	20	5.0	A and F
6.	H.K.U.S.T.	20	4	130	20	1.0	A
8.	K.I.T.	25	4	100	20	1.0	B
9.	N.T.U.	12.5, 25	3	125	25	1.0	C
11.	T.U.H.H.	20	5	200	55	2.0	A
14.	U.S.	25	3.8	170	65	0.5	D and E

*A = corrected beam theory (ESIS Protocol); B = modified compliance method (JIS K7086); C = load method; D = modified compliance method (ASTM 5528 - 94a); E = displacement method; F = area method.

Fig.2 Schematic geometry of the specimen for ILSS test:(a) and mode I interlaminar fracture toughness test:(b).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Short Beam Shear Test

Fig. 3 shows the ILSS values for composites with five different surface treatments. It can be noted here that the ILSS increased 10%~30% with increasing concentration of methacryl silane, regardless of the fiber orientation (warp or weft directions). This appears clearly on Fig.4. It is also noted that the ratio of increasing ILSS is slightly 20% higher in the weft direction than in the warp direction. This is probably related to the weave structure of the woven fabric used in this study. But in general the amplitude of the variations observed remain very low and lower than those observed between materials with different interface qualities. This suggests that the contribution of the fiber orientation is very small and could be perhaps neglected in regard to the contribution of the interface quality.

Fig.3 Interlaminar shear strength with five different surface treatments.

For a majority of laboratories, methanol washed specimen showed an increase in ILSS by 5%~20% in comparison with unwashed specimen. For 0.4 wt% epoxy silane finished specimens the lowest ILSS values were obtained among the composites with different surface treatments from all the participating laboratories. Regarding the effects of surface treatment on ILSS (nature of silane, methanol washing and amount of silane), it is finally interesting to note that the same general trends have been found previously on the basis of tensile and bending tests (strength values) [10].

Fig.4 Interlaminar shear strength of warp and weft specimens with concentration of methacrylsilane.

Mode I Interlaminar Fracture Toughness Test

Fig.5 shows typical load - displacement curves for warp and weft specimens with finished by 0.01 and 0.4 wt% methacryl silane. In the case of 0.01 wt% specimens, the load increased to the maximum load linearly, and decreased gradually after the maximum, with stable crack propagation. The maximum loads obtained from the weft specimen was higher than the warp specimen. On the other hand, the load-displacement curve displayed saw teeth like behavior for 0.4 wt% specimens. The load dropped suddenly after reaching the maximum load, and crack propagated unstably at fast speed for both the warp and weft specimens.

Fig.5 Typical load - displacement curves for warp and weft specimens: (a) 0.01wt% methacryl silane, (b) 0.4wt% methacryl silane.

Initiation values of mode I interlaminar fracture toughness G_{IC} , are shown in Fig.6. It is generally found that the weft specimens showed slightly higher G_{IC} , than the warp specimens,

for both silane concentrations, 0.01 and 0.4 wt%, except those reported from two laboratories. Especially, there was more difference between the weft and warp specimens in the 0.01 wt% specimen relative to the 0.4 wt% specimen. Unstable fracture occurred in the 0.4 wt% specimens so that the propagation value G_{IR} , could not be obtained. Fig.7 gives a comparison of the propagation values, G_{IR} calculated for 0.01 wt% specimens. Most laboratories reported that the propagation values, G_{IR} , were higher for the weft specimens than the warp specimens. It was also noted that the propagation values, G_{IR} , were higher than the initiation values, G_{IC} .

Fig. 6: Initiation values of mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of warp and weft specimens: (a) 0.01 wt% methacryl silane, (b) 0.4 wt% methacryl silane

The weft specimens had higher strands density in the longitudinal direction than the warp specimens as noted from Fig.1. As such, it is thought that crack propagation along the length of weft specimens may need more energy than along the warp direction. Accordingly, both

the initiation values G_{IC} , and propagation values G_{IR} , for the weft specimens were higher than the warp specimens. Concerning the increase of fracture toughness with crack propagation i.e., $G_{IR} > G_{IC}$, which is considered due to fiber bridging. Many researchers reported that fiber bridging gives rise to higher mode I interlaminar fracture toughness [11,12]. According to our observation, the fiber bridging builds up gradually with crack propagation.

Just as for ILSS results, the results obtained on the basis of mode I tests show that the influence of fiber orientation is far less than the influence of interface quality[10]. As over 100% variation was observed on G_{IC} initiation values with different surface treatments, only 10~20 % variation is noted when changing the fiber orientation. This confirms the fact that the interface quality plays here a role of prime importance on the damage mechanisms of such composites. The role of fiber orientation is less important.

Fig. 7 Propagation values of mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of the specimens finished with 0.01wt% methacryl silane.

CONCLUSIONS

The second Round Robin Test was carried out with twenty laboratories having participated globally to study the interlaminar fracture behavior of glass woven fabric vinylester composites with five different silane coupling agents. Short beam shear tests and mode I interlaminar fracture toughness tests were performed with the specimens whose directions were both weft and warp fiber orientations. Regarding the influence of the surface treatment, it could also be noted that in general the same trends previously observed for tensile and bending strengths are obtained for ILSS. A slight increase in both the initiation and propagation G_{IC} values was generally noted when changing the fiber orientation from warp to weft direction. Finally it is interesting to note that the amplitude of the variation of the properties (ILSS or mode I) is higher when modifying the surface treatment than when modifying the orientation of the fibers. This means that the purely interfacial effects are influencing more the damage mechanisms than the weave structure effects (at least for the glass / vinylester composite materials studied here).

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The organizers of the 2nd round robin test programme wish to thank all the participants who completed the test as instructed and submitted the results in time. A special gratitude is due to Dr. Y.Suzuki of Nitto Boseki Co. Ltd, Japan for supplying the glass woven fabrics used in this study.

REFERENCES

1. H.Hamada, N.Nishida, Z.Maekawa & N.Ikuta, Journal of Material Science, **29**, 352 (1994).
2. P.S.Chua & M.R.Piggot, Composite Science and Technology, **22** pp.33-42 (1987).
3. G.Dorey & J.Harvey, Interfaces in Polymer Ceramic and Metal Matrix Composites, pp.694 (1988).
4. L.T.Drzal, 28th National SAMPE Symposium, pp.1051 (1983).
5. E.Fitzer, K.H.Geigl, W.Huttner & W.Weiss, Carbon, **18** pp.389-393 (1980).
6. T.Norita, J.Matsui & H.S.Matsui, Composite Interfaces, pp.213-232 (1980).
7. Y.Suzuki, Z.Maekawa, H.Hamada, M.Kibune, M.Hojo & N.Ikuta, Journal of Material Science, **27** pp.6782-6790 (1992).
8. P.Krawczak & J.Pabiot, Journal of composite materials, **29** pp.2230-2253 (1995).
9. Y.Nakanishi & N.Ikuta, Journal of Society Material Science, **45** pp.1307-1315 (1996).
10. H.Saidpour, M.Sezen, Y.J.Dong, H.S.Yang, Y.L.Bai, T.X.Mao, C.Bathias, P.Krawczak, R.Bequignat, J.Pabiot, S.Pinter, G.Banhegyi, J.K.Kim, M.L.Sham, I.Verpoest, H.Hamada, Y.Hirai, K.Fujihara, C.Y.Yue, K.Padmanabhan, Y.Suzuki, T.Tanimoto, K.Schlute, J.K.Karger-Kocsis, W.J.Cantwell, R.Zulkifli, L.Ye, A.Lowe, S.V.Hoa, V.V Smirnov, L.T.Drzal, W.R Broughton & J.J.Lesko, to appear in Proc.ICCM-11.
11. M.Hojo & T.Aoki, ASTM STP 1156 pp.281-298 (1993).
12. X.Z.Hu & Y.W.Mai, Composites Science and Technology, **46** pp.147-156 (1993).